

Regional Assessment of the Seagrass *Syringodium filiforme* Kütz. in the Tropical Atlantic Seagrass Bioregion (Bioregion 2) for the IUCN Red List ¹

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PLANTAE - TRACHEOPHYTA - LILIOPSIDA - ALISMATALES - CYMODOCEACEAE - *Syringodium* - *filiforme*

Common Names: Manateegrass (English), Species code: Sf (English)

Synonyms: *Cymodocea filiformis* (Kütz.) Correll. not accepted (World Record of Marine Species WoRMS, 2025)
Cymodocea manatorium, not accepted (World Record of Marine Species WoRMS, 2025)

Red List Status
LC – Least Concern, (IUCN version 3.1)
Extent of Occurrence (EOO) in Bioregion 2= 8,323,708 km ²
Area of occupancy (AOO) in Bioregion 2= not determined

Red List Assessment

Assessment Information

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Publication date: 3rd June 2025

Time period assessed: 2007-2020

Assessment Rationale

Syringodium filiforme is an abundant species throughout its range, endemic to seagrass Bioregion 2. Its overall population appears stable, and some subpopulations are increasing (e.g., in formerly oligotrophic Caribbean reef lagoons; Van Tussenbroek et al. 2014). Such gains likely balance losses elsewhere (e.g., Florida, USA, Buzzeli et al. 2012). Threats include pollution and degraded water quality, decreased salinity due to excessive stormwater runoff or

¹ This regional assessment also constitutes the global assessment for this species, given that its global distribution is limited to the Tropical Atlantic Seagrass Bioregion.

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hurricanes and continued coastal development; however, the species has a great capacity for recovery once conditions improve. *S. filiforme* was previously listed as Least Concern (LC) by Short et al. (2010), and remains so for the 2007-2020 time period.

Distribution

Geographic Range

Syringodium filiforme is only found in Tropical Atlantic Seagrass Bioregion. It occurs in the western central Atlantic from Florida, USA to Venezuela, throughout the Gulf of Mexico and the Caribbean Sea. It is also found in Bermuda.

Elevation / Depth / Depth Zones

Depth Lower Limit (in metres below sea level): ~20 m (Duarte, 1991).

Depth Upper Limit (in metres below sea level): 0

Depth Zone: Shallow photic (0-50m); usually between 0-10m depth (Duarte, 1991)

Map Status

Map Status	How the map was created, including data sources/methods used:	Please state reason for map not available:	Data Sensitive?	Justification	Geographic range this applies to:	Date restriction imposed:
Done	<p>EOO only. The extreme distribution points were verified from Juman & Alexander (2006), van Tussenbroek et al. (2014), Congdon & Dunton (2016), Arrellano-Méndez et al. (2019) and Vera et al. (2021). Other occurrence points defining the EOO polygon were sourced and verified from Seagrass Spotter (https://seagrassspotter.org/sightings/map) and Global Biodiversity Information Facility (https://www.gbif.org)</p>	-	-	-	Bioregion 2	-

Occurrence

Countries of Occurrence ²

Country	Presence	Origin	Formerly Bred	Seasonality
Anguilla	Extant	Native	-	Resident
Antigua and Barbuda	Extant	Native	-	Resident

² This listing includes countries from this regional assessment and those reported for Bioregion 2 in the previous global assessment of *Syringodium filiforme* (Short et al. 2010).

Aruba	Extant	Native	-	Resident
Bahamas	Extant	Native	-	Resident
Barbados	Extant	Native	-	Resident
Belize	Extant	Native	-	Resident
Bermuda	Extant	Native	-	Resident
Bonaire, Sint Eustatius and Saba	Extant	Native	-	Resident
Bonaire, Sint Eustatius and Saba -> Bonaire	Extant	Native	-	Resident
Bonaire, Sint Eustatius and Saba -> Saba	Extant	Native	-	Resident
Bonaire, Sint Eustatius and Saba -> Sint Eustatius	Extant	Native	-	Resident
Cayman Islands	Extant	Native	-	Resident
Colombia	Extant	Native	-	Resident
Costa Rica	Extant	Native	-	Resident
Cuba	Extant	Native	-	Resident
Curaçao	Extant	Native	-	Resident
Dominica	Extant	Native	-	Resident
Dominican Republic	Extant	Native	-	Resident
Grenada	Extant	Native	-	Resident
Guadeloupe	Extant	Native	-	Resident
Guatemala	Extant	Native	-	Resident
Haiti	Extant	Native	-	Resident
Honduras	Extant	Native	-	Resident
Jamaica	Extant	Native	-	Resident
Martinique	Extant	Native	-	Resident
Mexico	Extant	Native	-	Resident
Montserrat	Extant	Native	-	Resident
Nicaragua	Extant	Native	-	Resident
Panama	Extant	Native	-	Resident
Puerto Rico	Extant	Native	-	Resident
Saint Kitts and Nevis	Extant	Native	-	Resident
Saint Lucia	Extant	Native	-	Resident
Saint Martin (French part)	Extant	Native	-	Resident
Saint Vincent and the Grenadines	Extant	Native	-	Resident
Sint Maarten (Dutch part)	Extant	Native	-	Resident
Trinidad and Tobago	Extant	Native	-	Resident
Turks and Caicos Islands	Extant	Native	-	Resident
United States of America	Extant	Native	-	Resident
Venezuela, Bolivarian Republic of	Extant	Native	-	Resident
Virgin Islands, British	Extant	Native	-	Resident
Virgin Islands, U.S.	Extant	Native	-	Resident

FAO Area Occurrence

Presence Origin Formerly Bred Seasonality			
31. Atlantic - western central	Extant	Native -	Resident

Regional Assessment Map ³

³ EOO was obtained using minimum bounding geometry/convex hull from ArcGIS Pro, giving the smallest polygon enclosing all points of occurrence.

The general status of *Syringodium filiforme* has not changed since the previous assessment by Short et al. (2010). It remains abundant and the range-wide populations appear to be stable; however, local population gains and losses have been reported since 2010.

Reports of population losses since last assessment (2007-2020):

- Extensive meadows dominated by *S. filiforme* in the Upper Laguna Madre, Texas, were almost entirely eradicated after an extended period of high salinity (50-70) during a regional drought in 2013 (Wilson & Dunton 2018).
- Mixed meadows of *T. testudinum* and *S. filiforme* on the Bermuda Platform were lost from 2007-2016 due to excessive grazing by green turtles (Fourqurean et al. 2019).
- In central and southern Biscayne Bay, Florida, mixed seagrass meadows with moderate abundance of *S. filiforme* were eradicated by a macroalgal (*Anadyomene* sp.) bloom, which persisted from 2005-2012 (Collado-Vides et al. 2013). In northern Biscayne Bay, between 2012 and 2017, roughly 500 ha of *S. filiforme*-dominated seagrass beds were lost. Eutrophication and degraded water quality were believed to be factors in the die-off (Fourqurean, pers. comm. in Miami-Dade Report 2019).
- Estuaries on the east coast of south Florida, suffered from decreased salinity (≤ 20) and submarine light (attenuation $\geq 1.5 \text{ m}^{-1}$) associated with increasing freshwater runoff during hurricanes in 2005, resulting in a widespread decrease in the coverage and biomass of *S. filiforme* in 2006 (Buzzelli et al. 2012, and references therein). Hurricane Irma made landfall in the state of Florida in 2018, affecting the open water and watersheds in six estuaries in SW Florida. In response, seagrass (including *S. filiforme*) coverage declined by 1,203 ha between 2016 and 2018, a system-wide decrease of 3% (Tomasko et al. 2020).
- In W-Florida, acreage of the seagrass meadows (including *S. filiforme*), declined in Sarasota Bay area attributed to high nitrogen content in water causing suffocating algal blooms (Sarasota County 2019). In the Indian River Lagoon, seagrass communities have lost more than 50% of their pre-bloom areal extent in response to chronic, widespread phytoplankton blooms since 2011; *S. filiforme*, previously the second most common species in the system, has been nearly extirpated in the northern (temperate) portion of the system and vastly reduced south of the subtropical Sebastian Inlet (Morris et al., 2022).
- Locally, the introduced seagrass *Halophila stipulacea* can replace native seagrasses such as *S. filiforme* (Willette et al. 2014 and references therein).
- Ongoing from 2011 to date, near-shore fringes of seagrass meadows with moderate or abundant *S. filiforme* have been severely affected by massive beaching of holopelagic *Sargassum* spp. (creating “sargassum brown tides”) caused by the basin-scale bloom of these algae (Van Tussenbroek et al. 2017). *S. filiforme* is amongst the first species to recolonize these zones when the sargassum brown tides recede, indicating high recovery potential (unpublished data B.I. van Tussenbroek)

Report of increase or recovery or extension of populations since last assessment:

- According to a Caribbean-wide, long-term study (CARICOMP) of seagrass beds in (originally oligotrophic or mesotrophic) reef lagoons, conducted at 22 sites with 52 sampling stations, the relative abundance of *S. filiforme* increased at most sites from 1993 until 2012 likely caused by decreasing water quality (decreasing transparency and/or increasing nutrient input); which favors faster growing species such as *S. filiforme* over *Thalassia testudinum*. (van Tussenbroek et al., 2014)
- *S. filiforme* has contributed to the increases that Tampa Bay has enjoyed over the last 20+ years. Sherwood et al. 2017 mentioned “Large increases in manatee grass coverage were also estimated (2,354 ha) between 1999 and 2014”. Although not species-specific, the regional gains in seagrass in SW Florida reported in Tomasko et al. 2018 include gains by *S. filiforme*, which resulted from resource management plans reducing point sources of nitrogen loads allowing for expansion of seagrass meadows.
- A mixed seagrass meadow of *T. testudinum* and *S. filiforme* in Puerto Rico showed a 64% increase in size from 1950 until 2014; attributed to recovery from a severe hurricane in 1950, and decreasing grazing pressure in the area (León Pérez et al. 2020).
- Recent mapping efforts of the seagrass meadows in the more or less turbid water of Campeche Bank, Mexican Gulf of Mexico, revealed enormous extensions of meadows dominated by *S. filiforme* (360 km²) between ≈ 4 and 7 m depth (Perez-Espinoza et al. 2019).
- Excessive sea turtle (*Chelonia mydas*) grazing has led to local declines in abundance or structural complexity of the dominant seagrass species *T. testudinum* in the Caribbean (e.g., Fourqurean et al. 2019, Molina Hernández & Van Tussenbroek 2014). This decrease in *T. testudinum* canopy from grazing has led to increases of faster growing seagrass species such as *Halodule wrightii*, *S. filiforme* or rhizophytic algae (Molina Hernández & Van Tussenbroek 2014; Martinez-Lopez et al. 2019). Grazing and a subsequent decline in *T.*

testudinum canopy structure has led to increased cover of faster growing species such as *S. filiforme* and *H. wrightii* at a long-term monitoring site on the Caribbean coast of Costa Rica (Moya-Ramirez et al. 2025).

Population Information

Continuing decline in mature individuals?	Qualifier	Justification
-	-	-

Continuing decline in number of subpopulations	Qualifier	Justification
-	-	-

Habitats and Ecology

Syringodium filiforme is typically found on sand to mud bottoms up to 20 m depth (e.g. Steiner et al. 2010), but it can occur deeper in transparent waters (Kenworthy & Fonseca 1996). Recent seagrass mapping or monitoring programs found that this species often grows intermixed with *Thalassia testudinum*, and/or *Halodule wrightii* in the Gulf of Mexico (Browder et al. 2013, Congdon & Dunton 2016, Yarbro & Carlson 2016, Perez-Espinosa et al. 2016) and the Caribbean (Van Tussenbroek et al. 2014), but also grows in extensive almost mono-specific meadows (e.g., Campeche, Gulf of Mexico- Perez-Espinosa et al. 2016, Dominica, Caribbean - Steiner et al. 2010, Texas-Gutierrez et al. 2010, and SW Florida – Fourqurean et al. 2001).

A Caribbean-wide study (Van Tussenbroek et al. 2014-other seagrasses=*S. filiforme*), found the total biomass varying between 15.3-1,066.0 dry g m⁻² (median 101.5 dry g m⁻²) at 22 stations where this species was recorded. Above-ground biomass varied between 3.5-140.9 dry g m⁻² (median 16.5 dry g m⁻²), corresponding with an aboveground/total biomass ratio of 6.2-21.6% (median 15.6%).

S. filiforme is a fast-growing colonizing species, quickly revegetating disturbed areas due to natural or human-induced disturbances (e.g., Furman et al. 2018). It can grow deeper than *T. testudinum*; for example, Manuel et al. (2013) reported *T. testudinum* until 9 m depth on the Bermuda platform, whereas *S. filiforme* grew until 15m depth, requiring respectively 57 and 47% of surface irradiance. In turbid waters, this species grows much shallower, on average 1.5-2 m depth at Ten Thousand Islands, Florida, USA (Slone et al. 2013).

Along the Gulf of Mexico coast of Texas (Bittner et al. 2020) and Florida (Choice et al. 2014), suitable habitat for *S. filiforme* could best be predicted by benthic light availability, which tends to decrease with increasing human development and nutrient water concentrations. This species does not grow in brackish areas (Short et al. 2010 & references therein), and extensive meadows of the species were lost when exposed to low salinities (≤ 20) after freshwater runoff due to hurricane impacts in Florida estuaries (Buzzelli et al. 2012).

S. filiforme can be heavily grazed by fish (e.g., juvenile parrotfish - Bourque & Fourqurean 2013; or parrotfish, pinfish and filefish – Prado & Heck 2011), and is an important food source for manatees (Allen et al. 2018; Lefebvre et al. 2017). Other species grazing on this seagrass species are surgeonfish, sea urchins (Eklöf et al. 2008), and sea turtles (e.g., Fourqurean et al. 2019). Juvenile fish species of the families Tetraodontidae and Scaridae (*Sphoeroides spengleri*, *Canthigaster rostrata*, *Sparisoma rubripinne*) eat the male flowers of this species (Van Tussenbroek & Muhlia 2013).

The cylindrical leaves of *S. filiforme* break off easily, after which they float to the surface, at times forming floating aggregations that may remain afloat for months; often it is the principal species in wrack on the tropical beaches (excluding the recent massive beaching events of the holopelagic *Sargassum* spp.). The pelagic seagrass aggregations may provide organic carbon and nutrients to off-shore waters (Perry et al. 2018).

IUCN Habitats Classification Scheme

Habitat	Season Suitability	Major Importance?
9.4. Marine Neritic -> Marine Neritic - Subtidal Sandy	- Suitable	-
9.5. Marine Neritic -> Marine Neritic - Subtidal Sandy-Mud	- Suitable	-
9.6. Marine Neritic -> Marine Neritic - Subtidal Muddy	- Suitable	-
9.8.2. Marine Neritic -> Marine Neritic - Coral Reef -> Back Slope	- Suitable	-
9.8.4. Marine Neritic -> Marine Neritic - Coral Reef -> Lagoon	- Suitable	-
9.8.5. Marine Neritic -> Marine Neritic - Coral Reef -> Inter-Reef Soft Substrate	- Suitable	-
9.9. Marine Neritic -> Marine Neritic - Seagrass (Submerged)	- Suitable	-
9.10. Marine Neritic -> Marine Neritic - Estuaries	- Suitable	-
12.2. Marine Intertidal -> Marine Intertidal - Sandy Shoreline and/or Beaches, Sand Bars, Spits, Etc	- Suitable	-

Life History

Generation Length	Justification	Data Quality
2	-	-

Syringodium filiforme is capable of maintaining its populations exclusively through vegetative (clonal) growth by extension of the rhizomes. This species has a high clonal expansion rate attaining rhizome elongation rates between 52-182 cm per year (e.g., Marbà & Duarte 1998), and the shoots on a rhizome section are physiologically integrated (Schwarzschild & Zieman 2008).

S. filiforme is a dioecious species with male and female inflorescences (cymes) on separate plants (Van Tussenbroek et al. 2010). Sexual reproduction is seasonally synchronized (from late winter throughout the summer) in the Gulf of Mexico (McMillan 1980), Mexican Caribbean (Van Tussenbroek & Muhlia Montero 2013) and Costa Rica, where environmental cues such as light, temperature and tidal range influenced the timing of sexual reproduction (Samper-Villarreal et al. 2020). There are indications that pollen limitation may occur in this species (Van Tussenbroek & Muhlia Montero 2013). This species has a high seed set, up to 9,000 seeds m⁻² y⁻¹ in the Gulf of Mexico (McMillan 1981). Guzmán-Trampe (2009) found a seed production of up to 5,000 seeds per m⁻² y⁻¹ in a Caribbean Reef Lagoon. Despite this, little is known about seed viability, seed bank dynamics or seedling survival (Orth et al. 2016).

In Florida, Bermuda and Bahamas, *S. filiforme* showed population genetic characteristics typical for a colonizer species, such as variable genotypic diversity and low genetic (within population allelic) diversity. Clonal diversity was low to moderate (R between 0.04 and 0.62). Patterns in geneflow were asymmetric, with significant differentiation between the Atlantic and Gulf of Mexico populations (Bijak et al. 2018).

Breeding Strategy

Does the species lay eggs?

NA

Does the species give birth to live young

NA

Does the species exhibit parthenogenesis

NA

Does the species have a free-living larval stage?

NA

Does the species require water for breeding?

NA

Systems

System: Marine

Threats

Threats affecting *Syringodium filiforme* are eutrophication and sedimentation, or localized decreases in salinity.

Coastal development, pollution from land-based sources and eutrophication (sewage and agricultural fertilizers) are local threats throughout the Greater Caribbean region. In Florida, this species is locally affected by sewage pollution from expanded residential and hotel development, and marina and boat usage. It is also incidentally damaged from boat traffic. In the Yucatan Peninsula, this species can be affected locally by trawling, eutrophication, and port development. In Texas, *S. filiforme* mortality occurred following an extended period of extremely high salinity (salinities 50–70) during a regional drought (Wilson & Dunton 2018). Locally, the introduced seagrass *H. stipulacea* may displace native seagrasses like *S. filiforme* and *H. wrightii* (Willette & Ambrose 2012, Muthukrishnan et al. 2020); although Van Tussenbroek et al (2016) observed that the nonnative species mainly obtained invasive characteristics in eutrophicated disturbed sites. It has been experimentally demonstrated that *S. filiforme* is susceptible to biomass loss to herbivory, as shown experimentally (Bourque & Fourqurean 2013) and in situ due to urchin grazing in Florida Bay (Rose et al. 1999). At Barbados, a meadow dominated by *S. filiforme* collapsed after being decimated by sea urchins, followed by a sea-height anomaly (Van Tussenbroek et al. 2014).

Conservation

This species has been monitored by the CARICOMP network (Caribbean Coastal Marine Productivity network; Van Tussenbroek et al. 2014; Cortes et al. 2019), and is monitored at some places by SeagrassNet (<http://www.seagrassnet.org/>). In Mexico, this species is protected under NOM-059 (Norma Oficial Mexicana; https://www.dof.gob.mx/nota_detalle_popup.php?codigo=5578808).

In Florida, USA, removal or destruction of any seagrass species, is prohibited and regulated through permit requirements and offset through mitigation. In some areas, seagrass meadows have been marked with signage and in others boat access has been limited to poling and trolling to decrease grounding and propeller scaring. In many areas damages can result in monetary penalty. There are also plans to decrease negative human impacts through educational efforts aimed at sports fishers and recreational boaters.

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